
Challenges Before Women Football Players

Rohan Sudhakar Adnaik

Kolhapur

Corresponding Author - Rohan Sudhakar Adnaik

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Abstract:

In Universal Human Rights declarations there is provision of 'Right to education' and 'Right to play' for every child. Unfortunately 'Play' is denied to the children of developing countries mainly due to some social and economic reasons. In India participation of women players is very less as compared to developed countries. Socio-economic conditions are mainly affecting on participation of women players in India especially in rural areas. Participation of women football players in rural areas of Kolhapur district is also affected due to some socio-economic constraints. Social customs, cultural restrictions, lack of support from schools, inadequate financial support etc. are some of the reasons. Football is a game of strength, stamina and speed. Rural women football players are always better in those physical fitness factors. Every year women football teams from rural area used to participate more at district school level tournaments than the teams from urban area. But the participation of women football players in rural area decreases as increase in their age. Socio-economic conditions of players produce obstacles in fulfilling their fundamental right. The present study is to put light on Challenges before rural women football Players. Mainly socio-economic problems of women football players in rural areas of Kolhapur district.

Keywords: Play, Women players, Rural area, Socio-economic condition.

Introduction:

Rural sports are games developed in the traditional times. Practiced since ages it can be seen taking place among people involved in rural areas. The games were involved in their daily lives, some them were based on daily hunting techniques such as running, throwing, jumping. Nowadays, most of the rural sport seems extinct. Thus the development of sports in India has become a necessity. The government needs to come forward as the rural sportspersons need proper sports kit, nourishment through specific diet. Unless the requirements are fulfilled there

is no possibility to develop India into a superpower that is expected to win major tournaments like Olympics, Commonwealth games, and other Asian level games. It is important to know the games that are recognized on the National level. Currently, People are more involved in cricket, football, tennis, and hockey. However, there are a majority of games that are played on national and international levels. They are Athletics, Kabaddi, Kho-Kho, Wrestling, Tug of War, Archery, Weightlifting and Volleyball to name a few. Sports, a transformative tool cuts culture, gender

and class barriers. It helps us in the overall growth of an individual. Also used as a form of entertainment and refreshments, activities relating to sports and physical education are essential components in our daily lives. It is a key to healthy living and has inspired communities. It prevents stress and helps us keep a good mental health.

The government of India started several sports schemes. It was to make it sure that the growth of rural sports continues to grow. Depending on the need, Rural Sports Program was launched in the year 1970-71. The main motive was to find hidden talent in rural areas. Other sports-based programs include Rajiv Gandhi Khel Abhiyan, Urban Infrastructure Scheme, Himalayan region sports festival, National Sports Talent contest. These schemes were defined under the National Sports Policy in the year 2001.

It is very unfortunate that 'Play' is denied to the children of developing countries because of the factors like wrongly directed educational policies, poverty, social customs, less importance to play than academics, attitude of teachers, parents and school administrators, urbanization etc. and India is no exception to it. Right to play, right to education & right to social security are the articles of Universal Human Rights declarations. The plight of women across the world is one of the major human rights issues, which need to be propagated so that women across the world can enjoy their freedom and liberty which every human being entitle to. In

India Sports is always second preference for parents. The participation of women in Indian sports is very less as compared to developed countries. Women in rural area are not encouraged to participate actively in sports. Socio-economic factors in India mainly affecting on participation of rural women in sports activities. Participation of women in rural areas in sports is a topic virtually ignored and undeveloped. Thus factors affecting the participation can be studied.

Now days, the participation of women players from rural areas is not good enough as compare to urban areas. In Kolhapur district most of the women Football teams participate at school level belongs to rural areas. It is seen that as per upper age group or increase in age, participation of women football teams and players from rural area decreases. Women player in rural areas are allowed to play up to the certain age limit by their parents. Parent of these players may afraid of transgression of our culture and social restrictions and customs. The main earning source in rural area is farming and the parents of these football players can't afford to spend money on sports equipment and facilities. The less respect from the society, insufficient financial support, inadequate sporting facilities, role of schools, less grants and scholarships from government and less contribution of district sports office etc. are some of the problems experiences by women football players from rural areas of Kolhapur district. Women football players from rural areas have great potential to represent at

higher level. But due to some socio-economic problems, these players are not finding proper track to make their career in sports. Socio-economic problems play a role of obstacle in fulfilling fundamental right of women. This study is mainly to put light on socio-economic constraints and genuine problems of players. To fulfill 'Right to play' of women players present study concludes with the contribution and the role of family, society, schools and government.

Importance of Sports in Rural Area:

Today, India lags behind many Asian countries in international sports. 20 percent of our population involves rural youth. These people are deprived of major sports facilities so there is a need of sports facility in the form of playgrounds, infrastructure for these people. Also they are affected by socio-economic problems. So it's very important to give proper attentions towards these issues to solve problems of rural female players.

Objectives:

1. To study the socio-economic challenges of women football

players from rural areas of Kolhapur district.

2. To study the impact of socio-economic challenges on participation of rural women players.

Database and Methodology:

Present study mostly relies on primary data. Primary data has been collected through sample survey. 60 women Football players from rural areas of Kolhapur district were randomly selected. All the randomly selected players had been participated at district school level football tournament for the academic year 2022 to 2025. Data collected by providing mixed type of questionnaire to all the players. All the randomly selected women football players were belonging to under-14, under-17 and under-19 age groups from different high schools and junior colleges. To study social and economic conditions of women players, opinion related to their family, society and school/Jr. college were taken into consideration.

Table No.1 - Social challenges of women football players.

Sr. No.	Social Problems	No. of Players out of 60	Percentage
1	Family	51	85 %
2	Society	44	73 %
3	School/Jr.college	34	57 %

Source: Primary data

Table no.1 reveals the social challenges of women players related to family, society and school/Jr.college.

85% players think they have Family Problems. Parents expect help

from players in housekeeping and want to make career in academics than sports.

73% players think they experiences problems from society. They think women players have to listen taunts and comments from society as they go outside for playing sports tournaments. Players never feels secure or free because they always think about transgression of our culture and social restrictions when they wear sports kit, go outside for playing.

57% players feel they don't get proper help from their schools/Jr. college. Sometimes players don't get proper help from teachers and classmates regarding their missing studies due to various tournaments. As a meritorious sportsperson, these players' experiences less respect from teachers and classmates as compare to toppers students in studies.

Table No.2 - Economic challenges of women football players

Sr.No.	Social Problems	No. of Players out of 60	Percentage
1	Family	54	90 %
2	Society	42	70 %
3	School/Jr.college	47	78 %

Source: Primary data

Table no.2 reveals the economic challenges of women players related to family, society and school/Jr.college.

90% players think they have serious economic problems in their family. Players restricted by their parents to spend more money to get sports material and sports related facilities. Main reason is income source of parents is farming and animal husbandry. Various expenses of women players are not affordable to parents when they participate at higher level i.e. at National or International Level.

70% women players don't get proper and enough financial help and support from society that is from relatives, villagers, political leaders, social activists, NGOs etc.

78% players feel their school/Jr.college doesn't support them if players suffer economic problems. Players don't get T.A., D.A. for every tournament. For students it is not easy and possible to purchase sports materials individually. Players don't get adequate sports material and facilities or scholarships from schools.

Table No.3 - Reason may decrease participation of women football players

Sr.No.	Reason	No. of Players	Percentage
1	Social	23	38 %
2	Economic	37	62 %
	Total	60	100 %

Source: Primary data

It is found that the main reason which may decrease participation of women football players is economic reason. 62% players think they may not participate in football in future due to

economic reason. While 38% players think they may not participate due to social reasons. It is important to highlight that the percentage of players who gives economical reason is significant.

Table No. 4 - Participation of Teams for the academic year 2022 to 2025.

Sr.No.	Year	Kolhapur District Level Tournament		
		Under - 14	Under - 17	Under - 19
1	2022-23	08	06	03
2	2023-24	13	10	04
3	2024-25	11	8	02

From Table no.4 it is clear that the participation of women football teams at under-14 age group is more than under-17 age group for all the three academic years. Similarly participation of teams at under-17 age group is more than under-19 age group. One football team contains 16 players. Decrease in one team means decrease of all 12 players. From the table it is clear that as age and age group of women football player increases, participation of these players decreases significantly.

Conclusion:

Women football players in rural areas of Kolhapur district have some serious socio-economic challenges. Their Problems start from family. Career in academics than sports is the main expectation of their parents. Due to genuine economic family problems, players can't participate freely in sports. Society restricts players to improve their

natural and growing talent by giving importance to social customs. Overall development of a child is always a main responsibility of Schools/Jr. colleges. But lacuna in educational sports policies is demoralizing rural women football players. This lacuna is due to lack of Government grants & funds to school for sports. These socio-economic conditions may affect directly on overall developmental process of rural women players. All these problems directly make effect on the participation of rural women football players in sports. We can say socio-economic problems of rural women football players are the main obstacle for participate more in different level tournaments.

Suggestions:

Attitude of parents must change. Sports awareness of parents should be increase. Sports should be compulsory part of curriculum at school level. Provide

effective and modern coaching can find natural talent in student. Players must get enough time for physical training, adequate sports material, financial help, proper respect and motivation.

Society should respect the values and ethics of sports. Financial support from NGOs, social activists, political leaders etc. can boost enough confidence of players. Felicitation of meritorious player at social events/programs

Government should provide adequate sports materials to women players. Well-equipped sports centers, grounds to attract women for more participate. Sports scholarships to women players, different grants to schools, funds to private sports academies can solve financial problems of women football players.

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